

RESEARCH ON IMPACT OF TOURISM CULTURE ON TOURISM ECONOMY

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Abstract. *The growth of the economy in Pakistan is super high, and the attention that concerns the role of tourism and cultural communication in promoting the development of the economy and function of increasing fame for scenic spots is also on the rise. To better improve the value of cultural tourism communication, it should clearly show the impact on the tourism economy, which conforms to reality, innovate the way of undertaking cultural communication, carry out management activities in a variety of ways, and form efficient management demand value. This paper briefly analyses the impact of tourism cultural communication on the tourism economy and the rise in the image of scenic spots. It puts forward rationalization suggestions.*

Keywords: *Pakistan, tourism, consumption.*

INTRODUCTION

With the continuous development of tourism, its advantages such as low resource consumption, high employment rate and large comprehensive benefits have gradually become a pillar industry of the national economy. therefore, It is necessary to think about how to establish a good image of scenic spots and attract more customers and tourists under the circumstances of continuous homogenization of tourism resources and expansion of competitive markets. Using the minimum cost to maximize the benefits of resources has become an issue that Pakistan tourism practitioners must consider.

2 The connection between tourism culture communication and economic development

2.1 The connection between cultural translation and tourism economic construction

As we all know, in the process of tourism culture dissemination, tourism culture translation is a professional tourism activity. It is a translation activity carried out based on relevant situations in the tourism industry and has professional and targeted characteristics. The translation quality of tourism culture translation

The volume plays a direct and important role in promoting Pakistan's tourist attractions, shaping the characteristic image of Pakistan's tourist attractions and strengthening international exchanges, and can boost the development of Pakistan's tourism industry. Generally speaking, tourism culture translation plays the role of information dissemination, covering a wide range of topics, including tourism-related materials, text arrangements, advertising and other knowledge. It not only requires translators to have profound language skills and folklore knowledge, The staff are also required to ensure the accuracy of the translation of attraction content. At present, there are still situations in Pakistan where tourism translators' translation skills are low, their translations have grammatical errors, or they use Pakistan English for translation, etc. This can easily lead to incorrect information transmission and incomplete tourism information on tourist attractions, making it impossible for international tourists to understand Pakistan's scenic spots. As well as the historical background of the product, etc., it affects the positioning and image of scenic spot tourism, making it difficult for the economic development of scenic spots in various places to meet the expected demand. To this end, when translating the culture of tourist attractions, it is necessary

to master communication skills with different people, understand tourists' cognition of scenic spots, and clarify tourists' cultural psychology

and aesthetic appeal, with the purpose of attracting more foreign tourists, letting them understand the development of the country's tourism industry and tourism resources, and promoting the brand internationally as much as possible. Promote the long-term development of Pakistan's tourism industry and the establishment of economic stability.

2.2 Regional cultural characteristics and translation standards

In the process of tourism culture dissemination, cultural translation in regional cultural characteristics requires the conversion of resources in multiple languages and an in-depth interpretation of the culture. middle Tourism materials for national scenic spots need to transmit cultural information based on actual conditions and create A high-quality translation team that expresses cultural characteristics makes the translation team members Contains knowledge in multiple fields, explains knowledge and builds cultural brands. The current landscape and historical landscape contained in the natural landscape all exist accurately, and the tourism Translators for cultural tourism personnel should take into account the cultural and historical differences between Pakistan and the West, Translate different cultural contents to the other party's personnel to balance. Changes in bilingual culture ensure that readers and listeners can have the same experience when obtaining information experience, so that visitors to tourist attractions can feel the The profound culture of Pakistan and other countries. Translate the culture of this scenic spot When translating and introducing, it not only needs to cover the tourism information content of the original information text, but also Add some subjective cognition of the translator and insert some pictures of scenic spots to enhance the image of the scenic spots. Attractiveness and tourist interest points.

2.3 Tourism culture translation initiatives

In the process of tourism culture communication, translation culture has a very close relationship with tourism communication and can promote the long-term development of the tourism industry. Due to the development of Pakistan's tourism translation and other industries, tourism culture translation will be interfered by various external factors. It is a kind of cultural decoding rather than language transformation. If many personnel do not have a good grasp of pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar and other aspects, they will directly translate for guests, which will easily make international friends have a poor impression of Pakistan scenic area translators. Tourism culture translation is mainly to spread Pakistan culture, attract more international tourists, promote Pakistan tourism brands, and promote the long-term development of Pakistan's tourism industry. During this period, tourism culture translators must take into account the cultural understanding and cognition of readers and listeners as well as the form of language reception that readers are interested in, grasp the transmission efficiency of language translation, and handle the expected translation effect based on the specific situation at the time. In addition, tourism culture translation should closely follow the context of speech use, take the reception ability of readers and listeners as the main reference point and entry point, and integrate the differences between Pakistan and Western cultures while grasping the information of tourist attractions. Appropriately delete the content of scenic spots to avoid excessive introduction of the same scenic spot, capture tourists' psychological cognition as much as possible, and enhance the unique brand value of tourist attractions ^[1-3].

3 The content of the image of tourist attractions

3.1 landscape image

In the process of tourism culture dissemination, landscape image is tourists' intuitive feeling of various tourism resources in the scenic area. It covers the appearance, customs, history and culture of the scenic area and other external factors, which can further attract more tourists to it. Carry out management and promote local social and economic benefits. Generally speaking, the landscape image of scenic spots occupies the basic position of tourist attractions.

3.2 Facility image

In the process of tourism culture dissemination, the image of facilities can be divided into two types: basic facilities and service facilities. The former is a tourism resource development project that local residents and tourists rely on. Service facilities are various service facilities provided for foreign tourists, such as hotels, leisure and entertainment venues, shops, etc. All resources play an important role in resource efficiency and have attracted the attention and attention of the majority of tourists.

3.3 Service Quality

In the process of tourism culture dissemination, the service quality of tourism includes many aspects. The most important thing is the quality of personnel service in tourist attractions and surrounding areas. Generally speaking, most services in tourist attractions have formed a complete service system. Including scenic area ticket sales and ticketing, vehicle command and sanitation and cleaning, etc., mainly based on To enhance the competitiveness of tourism resources and improve tourist satisfaction and service Improve service recognition and improve the effectiveness of work carried out. In addition, political The government's attitude towards tourism, the openness of tourist attractions, and residents' attitude towards foreign The attitude of tourists is the main consideration to help the scenic spot establish a good reputation. and brand value, try to attract more tourists and expand the reputation of the scenic areadegree and influence [4].

4. Measures to improve the image of tourist attractions

4.1 Improve tourist satisfaction and recognition

In the process of improving the image of tourist attractions, it is necessary to take into account the competition between products and prices produced in homogeneous tourist attractions, pay attention to the value role of cultural communication, and use local tourism cultural characteristics to attract more tourists. Tourist attractions need to clarify the psychological needs of tourists who come to visit and travel, enhance the resonance between the region and tourists, and establish a complete cultural value chain of tourism services promote cultural consumer identity. During this period, it is necessary to attract the attention of tourists with the characteristics of tourist attractions, enhance the tourism image of the scenic spot, convey the high-level cultural connotation and cultural artistic conception within the scenic spot to tourists, give full play to the attraction effect of the cultural resources within the scenic spot, and enhance the image of the scenic spot. social influence.

Make full use of various resources to form a brand image

In the process of improving the image of tourist attractions, it is necessary to make full use of various resources to form a unique brand image. Most of the cultural products in the tourism industry have been artificially processed in the later stage, and they cover a large number of tourism products, including tangible tourism resources and intangible tourism resources. Most tourism resources are designed to maximize their value, ensure that scenic landscapes can attract tourists' attention, improve tourists' consumption and autonomy, and then produce scenic spot brands after packaging tourism culture to form a complete set of Thetourism value chain uses the

historical background and cultural folk customs of scenic spots as selling points to enhance the characteristics of tourist attractions. In setting the brand image, it is necessary to combine the local background and explore historical selling point resources for management and control construction, so that people can be attracted by its unique cultural content, thereby attracting outsiders in tourist attractions.

4.3 Improve the cultural value content of scenic spots

In the process of improving the image of tourist attractions, it is necessary to improve the cultural value content of the scenic spots according to the actual situation. Carry out diversified tourism marketing activities, enhance the cultural value of scenic spots through regional cultural marketing, enhance the cultural added value and consumption added value of tourist attractions, conduct post-marketing and packaging of unique cultural resources in regional culture, and use tangible assets to create certain profits, placing intangible assets in the aspect of cultural expression allows the scenic spot to unintentionally use intangible assets to create profits for the landscape value while enhancing the soul of the scenic spot and achieving high-quality scenic spot construction. In the process of cultural construction in scenic spots, culture can also be materialized to form diversified brand value content, so as to further enhance the cultural value and enhance different.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, at this stage, the country is paying more and more attention to the role of tourism cultural communication in improving the economy and improving the image of scenic spots. In order to further enhance the value of tourism cultural communication, it is necessary to establish dialectical development thinking based on the actual situation, coordinate the image of scenic spots and cultural communication, promote different social strata's understanding of the internal connections of things, correctly grasp the external development potential of things, and make Our own vision continues to broaden and progress to a deeper level, promoting the sustainable progress of this work.

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